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A STUDY ON WOMEN CONSUMERS' ATTITUDE OF PURCHASING CAR WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO PALAKKAD CITY

M. Saravanan,

Assistant Professor, PG Department of International Business,
Sree Narayana Guru College, K.G.Chavadi Coimbatore ,India

K. Soumya,

Research Scholar in Commerce,
Sree Narayana Guru College, K.G.Chavadi, Coimbatore, India

ABSTRACT

In today's competitive world, every company has to study consumer purchasing power and behaviors prior to develop marketing plan for their product. This enables the marketer to understand who constitute the market, what and why the market buys, who participate in and influences the buying process, and how, when and where consumer buy. Buyer behavior is deeply rooted in psychology with dashes of sociology thrown in just to make things more interesting. Since every person in the world is different, it is impossible to have simple rules that explain how buying decisions are made. Car dependence is a process and not a state: car use changes as people get older and perhaps richer. In general, people are not forced to buy a car and then immediately adopt a life style. It is also a fact that once we buy a car we drive more and more and pay less attention to alternatives.

Key words: Consumer, Psychology, Dependence, Buying Behaviour.

INTRODUCTION

In today's competitive world, every company has to study consumer purchasing power and behaviors prior to develop marketing plan for their product. This enables the marketer to understand who constitute the market, what and why the market buys, who participate in and influences the buying process, and

how, when and where consumer buy. But such knowledge is critical for marketers since having a strong understanding of buyer behavior will help shed light on what is important to the customer and also suggest the important influences on customer decision-making. Using this information, marketers can create marketing programs that they believe will be of interest to customers. Buyer behavior is deeply rooted in psychology with dashes of sociology thrown in just to make things more interesting. Since every person in the world is different, it is impossible to have simple rules that explain how buying decisions are made. Contemporary approaches to business emphasize the importance of adopting a consumer focus. Marketing, in particular, begins and ends with the consumer from determining his or her needs to ensure post-purchase satisfaction.

BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF WOMEN

A far greater proportion of women are employed in less well-paid sectors, but women are making inroads in the higher echelons of business and as entrepreneurs. Of greater long-term significance is the gradual rise in women's wealth. The women have to set up independently and acquire their own assets at a young age.

DEPENDENCE OF CAR

The car market, in common with many other markets, has entered a competitive period in which although sales volume has increased, the motor industry remains a key indicator in the world economy. The nexus of related industries which depend for their continued expansion on the car point to its crucial position. The massive growth of cars has required a massive growth of roads. Car dependence is a reality for almost 80 percent of trips people make. Nevertheless, most people would not describe themselves as dependent, but rather see the car as providing independence, real financial saving and privacy. However, some people perceive effects of car use such as declining fitness due to lack of exercise or stress when stuck in traffic. About 80 percent of car owners may not imagine living without car. People who drive a lot tend to regard public transportation to be inferior quality, unmatched with their status and standards of living. The current driving trends indicate much more car use and fewer acceptable alternatives. In an attempt to reduce car travel, addressing the most cars dependent will be least successful.

CAR CONSUMPTION OF WOMEN

The car market, in common with many other markets, has entered a competitive period in which, although volume sales have increased, market values are declining as a result of high capacity, high levels of imports and market saturation. Women are still far more likely than men to live in households with no car, although the pattern is far more equal among younger men and women. Women's increased earning power and rising economic wealth therefore make them of growing importance in expanding car manufacturers' threatened sales targets. Clearly women are buying small, fuel-efficient cars in greater and greater numbers. This reflects women's responsibility attitude toward the environment as well as price consciousness.

OBJECTIVES

- To find out the attitude of women consumers in purchasing cars.
- To find out the factors that influence women car buyers.
- To find out the major information sources through which they come to know about the carmakers and models.
- To find out the price range that is preferred by women and the financial sources which they prefer to purchase cars
- To find out the preferences with regard to interior comforts, safety measures and other comforts that the carmakers offer.
- To find out the level of awareness with regard utility of cars among women consumers.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

The purpose of the study is to view the Women Consumers preferences and awareness about cars. Ever since the advent of information technology in India, there has been a steady increase in the number of

women employees in these industries. As these working women are paid with handsome of salaries by the companies and their working hours are varied, there is a need for them to have safe and secure transportation with a fair degree of privacy. These factors enable the women employee to purchase four wheelers of different brands. Yet another factor that encourages the women employee to purchase cars is the liberal loans offered by commercial banks and financial institutions. This also helps the automobiles industries to develop and launch the new products with wider variety of mix to meet the specification and demands of women consumers.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The opinions collected from one respondent cannot be taken as the opinion of the whole population. The result of the study is subjected to personal bias of people. The study is done in Palakkad city. So the opinions of the people outside the city are unknown. Validity and reliability of the data collected depend on the response given by the people. Sample size is limited to 200 only.

METHODOLOGY

The study was empirical in nature and was carried out to find the women consumers' attitude of purchasing car with special reference to Palakkad City. A standardized questionnaire method was administered in collecting data for the above study purpose. The sampling frame for this study was Women consumers'. Convenience sampling technique was selected as a sample design. The study is exclusively conducted in Palakkad City keeping in mind to find the price range, preference and level of awareness towards the purchasing of car. Simple Percentage and Chi square test were used for data analysis.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Asha V.S.(2012), highlighted that the Maruti motor car segment within the four-wheeler industry showed a distinct behavior, compared to the overall sales of four-wheeler. Most of the women consumers buy Alto car. It provides for increased comfort drivability, safety, economical and convenience as compared to other brands. The women consumers are satisfied with their after sale services. Most of the women opined that, the reason behind dealing with a particular brand is "Brand image". Preference to Alto car followed by Maruti and others. Kiran Kumar.D (2012) in the study an attempt has been made to the survey for improving the customer satisfaction of Hyundai four-wheelers. Many suggestions have been made to overcome the problems relating to Hyundai. The study had helped to gain more knowledge about the car industry. The customer is considered to be the prime focus in today's market as customers is the first person in the business. Saraswathi (2008) in her study on consumer satisfaction on post-sales service with reference to four-wheeler automobile industry in Hyderabad and Secunderabad reflected that Maruti, Hyundai and Tata were the main players in four-wheeler industry. The study indicated that most of the respondents were aware of the service centers and received reminders from dealers for free services. The study also found that most of the respondents were satisfied with the over-all service offered to them. Vidhya Shankar (2007) in her study, focused attention on the nature of various categorized of consumer perception of Hyundai car. The study points out that the selection of a particular brand of Hyundai car is due to the influence of product factors such during comfort, appearance availability of spares, price etc. Sawant (2007) did a study on buying of four-wheelers from 100 respondents within Goa. It was inferred from the study that the maintenance and mileage were an important criteria for respondents in the purchase decision process. People, in general, perceive a big difference in prices, suitability to lady drivers, and mileage and resale value amongst various models available in the market. Although, respondents did not consider the safety factor to be that important, they found that all models are more or less equally safe. The criteria that ultimately played a significant role in the purchase decision of respondents were: mileage, price, required maintenance, acceleration and maker's reputation.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTEPRETATION

TABLE NO: 4.1 - AGE LEVEL

S.No	Age Level	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	20-25	42	21
2	25-30	38	19
3	30-35	44	22
4	35-40	18	9
5	Above 40	58	29
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 21 percent belongs to the age group of 20-25 years, 19 percent belongs to the age group of 25-30 year, 22 percent belongs to the age group of 30-35 year, 9 percent belongs to the age group of 35-40 and 29 percent belongs to the age group above 40 years.

TABLE NO: 4.2 - MARITAL STATUS

S.No	Marital status	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Single	60	30
2	Married	140	70
	Total	200	100

Source: primary data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 30 percent of the Respondents are single and 70 Percent of the respondents are married people.

TABLE NO: 4.3 - EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION

S.No	Educational qualification	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	HSC	14	7
2	Diploma	4	2
3	Under graduate	52	26
4	Post graduate	122	61
5	Others	8	4
	Total	200	100

Source: primary data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 7 percent of respondents are having higher secondary qualification, 2 percent of the respondents are having Diploma qualification, 26 percent of respondents are having under graduate qualification, 61percent of respondents are having Postgraduate qualification and 4 percent are others.

TABLE NO: 4.4 - OCCUPATION

S.No	Occupation	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Business	10	5
2	Govt.employee	36	18
3	Private employee	58	29
4	IT professionals	50	25
5	Homemaker	46	23
	Total	200	100

Source: primary data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 5 percent of respondents are business women, 18 percent are government employees, 29 percent are private employees, 25 percent are IT professionals and 23 percent are homemakers.

TABLE NO: 4.5 - CAR USERS

S.No	People own a car	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	130	65
2	No	70	35
	Total	200	100

Source: primary data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 65 percent of respondents own a car and 35 percent do not own a car.

TABLE NO: 4.6 - DURATION OF CAR UTILITY

S.No	Duration of Car Usage	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	0-1 year	18	9
2	1-2 year	26	13
3	2-3year	68	34
4	3-4 year	22	11
5	Above 4 years	66	33
	Total	200	100

Source: primary data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 9 percent of the respondent are using car from 0-1 yr.13 percent were using car from 1-2 years, 34 percent were using car from 2-3 years, 11 percent were using car from 3 – 4 years and 33 percent were using car above 4 years

TABLE NO: 4.7 - CONSUMER PRICE PREFERENCES

S.No	Preferable Price Range	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Rs. 2.5 – 4.5 lakhs	92	46
2	Rs. 4.5 - 6.5 lakhs	90	45
3	Rs. 6.5 - 8.5 lakhs	14	7
4	Rs. 8.5 - 10.5 lakhs	2	1
5	Above Rs. 10.5 lakhs	2	1
	Total	200	100

Source: primary data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 46 percent of respondents prefer cars between Rs.2.5 - 4.5 lakhs, 45 percent prefer cars between Rs.4.5 - 6.5 lakhs, 7 percent prefer cars between Rs. 6.5 - 8.5 lakhs, 1 percent prefer car between Rs.8.5 - 10.5 lakhs and 1 percent prefer cars above Rs.10.5 lakhs.

TABLE NO: 4.8 - FINANCIAL SOURCES UTILIZED TO PURCHASE CAR

S.No	Financial Source	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Bank	78	39
2	Private financials	40	20
3	Loans through dealership	38	19
4	Own source of income	44	22
5	Lease	0	0
	Total	200	100

Source: primary data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 39 percent of respondents choose bank, 20 percent choose private financials, 19 percent choose loan through dealership and 22 percent purchase car with their own source of income.

TABLE NO: 4.9 - INFORMATION SOURCES TO PURCHASE CAR

S.No	Information Source	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	TV	22	11
2	Internet	34	17
3	Magazines	40	20
4	Referral	46	23
5	Walk into show room	58	29
	Total	200	100

Source: primary data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 11 percent of respondent's use TV, 17 percent use internet, 20 percent use magazines, 23 percent collect through referral and 29 percent walks into showroom to find out the information about car for purchase.

TABLE NO: 4.10 - COLOUR PREFERENCE

S.No	Colors	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Dark	52	26
2	Light	90	45
3	Bright	58	29
	Total	200	100

Source: primary data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 26 percent of the respondent prefer dark colors, 45 percent prefer light colors and 29 percent prefer Bright colors.

TABLE NO: 4.11

FIRST PREFERENCE TO INFLUENCE THE CHOICE OF PURCHASING CAR

S.No	Factors influence choice of Buying	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Cost	64	32
2	Fuel efficiency	22	11
3	Exterior appearance	10	5
4	Safety and reliability	54	27
5	Brand	50	25
	Total	200	100

Source: primary data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 32 percent give first preference for cost, 11 percent give first preference for fuel efficiency, 5 percent give first preference for exterior appearance, 27 percent give first preference for safety and reliability and 25 percent give first preference for brand.

TABLE NO: 4.12 - FIRST PREFERENCE ON INTERIOR COMFORTS

S.No	Interior Comforts	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Air conditioner	70	35
2	Power window	14	7
3	Enter / exit	56	28
4	Adjustable seating comforts	40	20
5	Adjustable safety belt	20	10
	Total	200	100

Source: primary data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 35 percent of the respondents give first preference to air conditioners. 7 percent give first preference to power windows, 28 percent give first preference to

enter/exit, 20 percent give first preference to adjustable seating comforts and 10 percent give first preference to adjustable safety belt.

TABLE NO: 4.13 - TYPES OF GEAR SYSTEM

S.No	Gear System	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Manual	48	24
2	Automatic	152	76
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 24 percent of respondents prefer manual transmission and 76 percent prefer automatic transmission.

TABLE NO: 4.14 - SAFETY MEASURES

S.No	Types of Safety Measures	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Central locking with test alarm	20	10
2	Central locking with remote	40	20
3	Low fuel warning lamp	50	25
4	Day and night mirror	16	8
5	Child safety rear door locks	74	37
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 10 percent of respondents would like to have central locking with test alarm as a safety measure, 20 percent would like to have central locking with remote, and 25 percent would like to have low fuel warning lamp, 8 percent would like to have day and night mirror and 37 percent would like to have child safety rear door locks. -

TABLE NO: 4.15 - PRIORITY ON EXTERIOR ATTRACTION

S.No	Exterior	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Alloy wheels	26	13
2	Ordinary wheels	4	2
3	Alloy wheels with tubeless tyres	52	26
4	Stylish body look	88	44
5	Bumpers	30	15
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that 13 percent of the respondents were attracted by alloy wheels, 2 percent of the respondents were attracted by ordinary wheels, 26 percent of the respondents were attracted by alloy wheels with tubeless tyres, 44 percent of the respondents were attracted by stylish body look and 15 percent of the respondents were attracted by bumpers.

TABLE NO: 4.16 - WARRANTY EXPECTED

S.No	Warranty Expected	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	1year	2	1
2	2 years	8	4
3	3 years	46	23
4	4 years	62	31
5	5 years	82	41
	Total	200	100

Source: primary Data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 1 percent of respondents expect 1 year warranty, 4 percent expect 2 years, 23 percent expect 3 years, 31 percent expect 4 years and 41 percent expect 5 years.

TABLE NO: 4.17 - DURATION OF CAR USAGE

S.No	Duration	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	2 years	12	6
2	3years	60	30
3	4years	30	15
4	5years	42	21
5	Above 5 years	56	28
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 6 percent of the respondents use the same car for 2 years only, 30 percent of the respondents use the same car for 3 years, 15 percent of the respondents use the same car for 4 years, 21 percent of the respondents use the same car for 5 years and 28 percent of the respondents use the same car for more than 5 years.

TABLE NO: 4.18

CAR USERS: WHAT CAR USER FEELS ABOUT CARS SEATS ARE COMFORTABLE

S.No	Seats are comfortable	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	124	62
2	Agree	72	36
3	Neutral	2	1
4	Disagree	2	1
5	Strongly Disagree	0	0
	Total	200	100

Source: primary data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 62 percent of the respondents strongly agree that their seats are comfortable, 36 percent agree 1 percent were neutral disagree respectively.

TABLE NO: 4.19 - AIR CONDITIONER WORKS WELL

S.No	Air Conditioner	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	120	60
2	Agree	70	35
3	Neutral	4	2
4	Disagree	6	3.
5	Strongly Disagree	0	0
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 60 percent of the respondents strongly agree that their air conditioner works well, 35 percent agree, 2 percent were neutral and 3 percent disagree.

TABLE NO: 4.20 - STORAGE SPACE IS ADEQUATE

S.No	Storage space are adequate	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	94	47
2	Agree	54	27
3	Neutral	8	4
4	Disagree	40	20
5	Strongly Disagree	4	2
	Total	200	100

Source: primary data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 47 percent of the respondents strongly agree that their storage space is adequate, 27 percent agree, 4 percent were neutral, 20 percent disagree and 2 percent strongly disagree.

TABLE NO: 4.21 - CAR ACCELERATE ADEQUATELY

S.No	Car accelerate adequately	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	90	45
2	Agree	98	49
3	Neutral	2	1
4	Disagree	6	3
5	Strongly Disagree	4	2
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 45 percent of the respondents strongly agree that their car accelerate adequately, 49 percent agree, 1 percent were neutral, 3 percent disagree and 2 percent strongly disagree.

TABLE NO: 4.22 - PARKING THE VEHICLE EASILY

S.No	Parking the Vehicle easily	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	76	38
2	Agree	68	34
3	Neutral	4	2
4	Disagree	48	24
5	Strongly Disagree	4	2
	Total	200	100

Source: primary data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 38 percent of the respondents strongly agree that they can park their vehicles easily, 34 percent agree, 2 percent were neutral, 24 percent disagree and 2 percent strongly disagree.

TABLE NO: 4.23 - VEHICLES HANDLES WELL IN THE CITY AND HIGHWAYS

S.No	Car handles in the city and highway well	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	94	47
2	Agree	92	46
3	Neutral	8	4
4	Disagree	4	2
5	Strongly Disagree	2	1
	Total	200	100

Source: primary data

Inference:

From the above table it is inferred that, 47 percent of the respondents strongly agree that their cars handles well in the city, and highways 46 percent agree, 4 percent were neutral. 2 percent were disagreeing and 1 percent were strongly disagreeing.

CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS

TABLE NO: 4.24 - AGE AND INFORMATION SOURCE TO PURCHASE CAR

Source Age	TV	Internet	Magazines	Referral	Walk into show room	Total
20-25	4	6	10	10	12	42
25-30	2	6	8	10	12	38
30-35	6	4	8	12	14	44
35-40	2	4	6	4	2	18
Above 40	8	14	8	10	18	58
Total	22	34	40	46	58	200

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between age and information source to purchase car.

At 5% level of significance, D.F.= 16, C.V.= 12.546, T.V. = 26.3

Since the calculated value is less than the table value, the null hypothesis is accepted, and hence we conclude that there is no relationship between age and information source to purchase car.

TABLE NO: 4.25 - MARITAL STATUS AND COLOUR PREFERENCE

Colour Marital Status	Dark	Light	Bright	Total
Single	16	24	20	60
Married	36	66	38	140
Total	52	90	58	200

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between marital status and colour preference.

At 5% level of significance, D.F.= 2, C.V. = 0.962, T.V.= 5.99

Since the calculated value is less than the table value, the null hypothesis is accepted, and hence we conclude that there is no relationship between marital status and colour preference.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

29 percent of the respondents belong to the age group of above 40 years. 70 percent of the respondents are married people. 61 percent of respondents are having Postgraduate qualification and 4 percent are others. 5 percent of respondents are business women, 18 percent are government employee, 29 percent are private employee, and 25 percent are it professionals and 23 percent are homemakers. 65 percent of respondents own a car and 35 percent do not own a car. 46 percent of respondents prefer cars between 2.5 - 4.5 lakhs and 45 percent prefer cars between 4.5 - 6.5 lakhs. 39 percent of respondents choose bank, 20 percent choose private financials, 19 percent choose loan through dealership and 22 percent purchase car with their own source of income. 11 percent of respondent's use TV, 17 percent use internet, 20 percent use magazines, 23 percent collect through referral and 29 percent walks into showroom to find out the information about car. 26 percent of the respondent prefers dark colors and 29 percent prefer Bright colors. 32 percent give first preference for cost, 27 percent give first preference for safety and reliability and 25 percent give first preference for brand. 35 percent of the respondents give first preference to air conditioners. 24 percent of respondents prefer manual transmission and 76 percent prefer automatic transmission. 10 percent of respondents would like to have central locking with test alarm as a safety measure and 37 percent would like to have child safety rear door lock. 13 percent of the respondents were attracted by alloy wheels and 44 percent of the respondents were attracted by stylish body look. 31 percent of the respondents expect 4 years warranty and 41 percent expect 5 years warranty. 21 percent of the respondents use the same car for 5 years and 28 percent of the respondents use the same car for more than 5 years. 62 percent of the respondents strongly agree that their seats are comfortable. 60 percent of the respondents strongly agree that their air conditioner works well. 47 percent of the respondents strongly agree that their storage space is adequate and 2 percent strongly disagree and feel that the storage space is not adequate. 45 percent of the respondents strongly agree

that their car accelerate adequately. 38 percent of the respondents strongly agree that they can park their vehicles easily, 24 percent disagree and 2 percent strongly disagree and said that parking their vehicles is not very easy. 47 percent strongly agree that their car handles well in the city and 46 percent agree that their car handles well in the highways.

SUGGESTIONS

The respondents were aware about cars through entire information source. So the company should come out with, the most effective dissemination of information about cars, through all possible advertisement strategy. Most of the respondents those who were highly aware about cars belong to the age group of 30 - 35, Hence the company should target the above age group to offer the car according to their preferences. The survey indicates that more respondents prefer low price models (Rs. 2.5 - 4.5 lakhs). Hence suggestions is made that manufacturer must offer car of above price range to women consumers. As more respondents prefer light colors with air conditioner facility in the cars, suggestions are made to the manufacturer to give high priority to these features. Further child safety rear door locks as safety measures and stylish exteriors are preferred by most of the consumers, Therefore manufacturer must have a conscience to these suggestions.

CONCLUSION

The most preferred car must be compact, air conditioned, stylish and safety measure such as child lock system. As the consumers belong to upper middle income group, the company should facilitate attractive loan offers by having tie-ups with commercial bank. High focus and weight age must be given to attribute preferred by women while launching the new product. The year of warranty they expect for a car shows that the awareness has reached the mass female. After sales service also considered by the women consumer, hence high priority should be given for after sales service with sufficient staff and networking infrastructure.

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